

AIR QUALITY INDEX FORECASTING VIA GENETIC ALGORITHM BASED IMPROVED EXTREME LEARNING MACHINE

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ABSTRACT

Air quality has always been one of the most important environmental concerns for the general public and society. Using machine learning algorithms for Air Quality Index (AQI) prediction is helpful for the analysis of future air quality trends from a macro perspective. When conventionally using a single machine learning model to predict air quality, it is challenging to achieve a good prediction outcome under various AQI fluctuation trends. In order to effectively address this problem, a genetic algorithm-based improved extreme learning machine (GA-KELM) prediction method is enhanced. First, a kernel method is introduced to produce the kernel matrix which replaces the output matrix of the hidden layer. To address the issue of the conventional limit learning machine where the number of hidden nodes and the random generation of thresholds and weights lead to the

degradation of the network learning ability, a genetic algorithm is then used to optimize the number of hidden nodes and layers of the kernel limit learning machine. The thresholds, the weights, and the root mean square error are used to define the fitness function.

Finally, the least squares method is applied to compute the output weights of the model. Genetic algorithms are able to find the optimal solution in the search space and gradually improve the performance of the model through an iterative optimization process. In order to verify the predictive ability of GA-KELM, based on the collected basic data of long-term air quality forecast at a monitoring point in a city in China, the optimized kernel extreme learning machine is applied to predict air quality (SO_2 , NO_2 , PM_{10} , CO , O_3 , $PM_{2.5}$ concentration and AQI), with comparative experiments based CMAQ (Community

Multiscale Air Quality), SVM (Support Vector Machines) and DBN-BP (Deep Belief Networks with Back-Propagation). The results show that the proposed model trains faster and makes more accurate predictions.

INTRODUCTION

Air pollution is a prevalent environmental problem in the twenty-first century. In light of the rapid industrialization and urbanization, air pollution is getting worse, which greatly affects our living environment and health [1]. Li et al. came to the conclusion that outdoor physical activity poses numerous health risks due to ambient air pollution in China. [2], [3]. According to the Chinese Ambient Air Quality Standards (GB3095-2012), there are six conventional air pollutants used to measure air quality: sulfur dioxide (SO_2), nitrogen dioxide (NO_2), particulate matter with a particle size less than 10 microns (PM_{10}), particulate matter with a particle size less than 2.5 microns ($PM_{2.5}$), ozone (O_3), and carbon monoxide (CO) [4], [5], [6]. These pollutants have adverse effects on human health. The International Energy Agency estimates that air pollution causes 6.5 million premature deaths per year, while long-term exposure to pollutants, such as fine particles (e.g., $PM_{2.5}$) or traffic-related pollutants, is linked to higher rates of lung cancer, coronary heart disease, and other

illnesses [7], [8]. Therefore, studies on air quality prediction are particularly important and are considered a key factor for environmental protection. In order to more comprehensively assess the health effects of air pollution, numerous air quality monitoring stations have been set up in major cities. Air quality predictions can be made based on the data collected from these stations. Air quality monitoring, modeling, and accurate predictions are important for having a clear understanding of future pollution levels and their associated health risks.

Recently, the inherent property of machine learning algorithm to automatically learn features at multiple level so abstraction has become increasingly important in providing solutions to this challenging task [9], [10]. However, the model only forecasts PM_{10} and SO_2 levels, and it is also challenging to obtain measurement values needed to construct the dataset [11]. Wu Q. et al. proposed an optimal-hybrid model for daily AQI prediction considering air pollutant factors, with the model's inputs being the six atmospheric pollutants. However, neural networks typically struggle with slow learning, a tendency to fall into local minima, and a complex network training process. Based on the generalized inverse matrix theory, Huang et al. proposed an

extreme learning machine (ELM) algorithm with a feedforward neural network that includes a single hidden layer, such that the problems of conventional neural network algorithms are circumvented. The ELM algorithm used to predict the AQI outperformed neural networks in terms of parameter selection, training speed, and prediction accuracy [12]. However, the parameters of the hidden layer nodes and the number of nodes in the test hidden layer are selected at random, which puts the prediction accuracy to a great test.

LITERATURE REVIEW

“A Bayesian LSTM model to evaluate the effects of air pollution control regulations in China,”

Rapid socio-economic development and urbanization have resulted in serious deterioration in air-quality in many world cities, including Beijing, China. This study attempts to examine the effectiveness of air pollution control regulations implemented in Beijing during 2008–2019 through a data-driven regulatory intervention analysis. Our proposed Bayesian deep learning model utilizes proxy data including Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD) and meteorology as well as socio-economic data, while accounting for confounding effects via propensity score estimation. Our

results show that air pollution control regulatory measures implemented in China and Beijing during 2008–2019 reduced PM_{2.5} pollution in Beijing by 11 % on average. After the introduction of Action Plan for Clean Air in China and Beijing in late 2013, as compared to the hypothetical PM_{2.5} concentration (without any regulatory interventions), the estimated PM_{2.5} reduction increased dramatically from 15 % in 2015 to 44 % in 2018.

Our results suggest that Beijing’s air quality has improved gradually over the past decade, though the annual PM_{2.5} pollution still exceeds the WHO threshold. In this regard, the air pollution control regulations introduced in Beijing and China tend to become more effective after 2015, suggesting a 2-year time lag before the stringent air pollution control regulations starting from 2013 takes any strong positive effects. Moreover, as compared to the air pollution control regulations introduced before 2013, newly introduced policy-making governance, which couples the policy-makings of the local jurisdictions with that of the central government, and the new policy measures that tackle the vested interests of the local stakeholders in Beijing and its nearby cities, alongside with the stringent local and national air pollution control regulations and plans, should help

reduce air pollution and promote healthy living in Beijing over the longer term.

“Air pollution forecasts: An overview,”

Air pollution is defined as a phenomenon harmful to the ecological system and the normal conditions of human existence and development when some substances in the atmosphere exceed a certain concentration. In the face of increasingly serious environmental pollution problems, scholars have conducted a significant quantity of related research, and in those studies, the forecasting of air pollution has been of paramount importance. As a precaution, the air pollution forecast is the basis for taking effective pollution control measures, and accurate forecasting of air pollution has become an important task. Extensive research indicates that the methods of air pollution forecasting can be broadly divided into three classical categories: statistical forecasting methods, artificial intelligence methods, and numerical forecasting methods. More recently, some hybrid models have been proposed, which can improve the forecast accuracy. To provide a clear perspective on air pollution forecasting, this study reviews the theory and application of those forecasting models. In addition, based on a comparison of different forecasting methods, the advantages and disadvantages of some methods of forecasting are also provided.

This study aims to provide an overview of air pollution forecasting methods for easy access and reference by researchers, which will be helpful in further studies.

“A deep learning approach to writer identification using inertial sensor data of air-handwriting,”

Owing to the increasing used mobile platforms (e.g., wearable devices or Virtual Reality) that lack of keyboard or camera to type passwords or capture visible data for user authentication, air-handwriting character/word-level writer identification systems have gained increasing attention [1]– [7]. Most of existing researches employ pen tip or finger tip movement (position data) for writer identification [1]– [6]. However, in order to obtain position data, more peripherals (e.g., cameras and infrared devices[8], [9]) are usually required. Such peripherals may be limited by light, background, etc. and the writer would have to hold his hand over the peripherals in the coverage area. In contrast to these peripherals, inertial sensor is not affected by environmental factors, and does not require the writer to write in a prescribed space, enabling true 3D air free writing. Besides, inertial sensor is less expensive. Therefore, the inertial sensor based model has a wide application scenario. Most previous methods rely heavily on sophisticated hand-designed

features for writer identification [2], [4]–[7].

“Application of computational intelligence techniques to forecast daily PM₁₀ exceedances in Brunei Darussalam,”

Particulate matter (PM₁₀) is the pollutant causing exceedances of ambient air quality thresholds, and the key indicator of air quality index in Brunei Darussalam for haze related episodes caused by the recurrent biomass fires in Southeast Asia. The present study aims at providing suitable forecasts for PM₁₀ exceedances to aid in health advisory during haze episodes at the four administrative districts of the country. A framework based on random forests (RFs), genetic algorithm (GA) and back propagation neural networks (BPNN) computational intelligence techniques has been proposed in which the final prediction is made by the BPNN model. A hybrid combination of GA and RFs is initially applied to determine optimal set of inputs from the initial data sets of largely available meteorological, persistency of high pollution levels, short and long term variations of emissions rates parameters.

The inputs selection procedure does not depend on the back propagation training algorithm. The numerical results presented in this paper show that the proposed model

not only produced satisfactory forecasts but also consistently performed better via several statistical performance indicators when compared with the standard BPNN and GA optimisation based on back propagation training algorithm. The model also showed satisfactory threshold exceedances forecasts achieving for instance best true predicted rate of 0.800, false positive rate of 0.014, false alarm rate of 0.333 and success index of 0.786 at Brunei-Muara district monitoring station. Overall, the current study has profound implications on future studies to develop a real-time air quality forecasting system to support haze management.

“Adopting Internet of Things for the development of smart buildings: A review of enabling technologies and applications,”

The 21st century is witnessing a fast-paced digital revolution. A significant trend is that cyber and physical environments are being unprecedentedly entangled with the emergence of Internet of Things (IoT). IoT has been widely immersed into various domains in the industry. Among those areas where IoT would make significant impacts are building construction, operation, and management by facilitating high-class services, providing efficient functionalities, and moving towards sustainable development goals. So far, IoT itself has

entered an ambiguous phase for industrial utilization, and there are limited number of studies focusing on the application of IoT in the building industry. Given the promising future impact of IoT technologies on buildings, and the increasing interests in interdisciplinary research among academics, this paper investigates the state-of-the-art projects and adoptions of IoT for the development of smart buildings within both academia and industry contexts.

“Hybrid spatio-temporal deep learning framework for particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) concentration forecasting,”

Urban environments globally are under threat due to recent climate changes caused by a variety of factors such as growing industrialization, rapid migration, increasing traffic flow, etc. An effective data-driven air pollution modeling system helps in increasing regular awareness regarding the severity of the air quality at the local level, play a preventive role in addressing the root causes and hence can be extremely useful for the urban administration. Graph Neural Networks have recently emerged for various classification and estimation tasks on graph-structured data. A Spatially Attentive Cluster-based Graph Neural Network-enabled PM_{2.5} concentration forecasting model (SA-GNN) is proposed to predict short-term PM_{2.5} concentrations by

considering monitoring stations as nodes of a graph structure and exploring their spatial relationships. This modeling procedure takes into account relevant meteorological variables like wind speed, wind direction, relative humidity etc.

“Optimization on fresh outdoor air ratio of air conditioning system with stratum ventilation for both targeted indoor air quality and maximal energy saving,”

Stratum ventilation can energy efficiently provide good inhaled indoor air quality with a proper operation (e.g., fresh outdoor air ratio). However, the non-uniform CO₂ distribution in a stratum-ventilated room challenges the provision of targeted indoor air quality. This study proposes an optimization on the fresh outdoor air ratio of stratum ventilation for both the targeted indoor air quality and maximal energy saving. A model of CO₂ concentration in the breathing zone is developed by coupling CO₂ removal efficiency in the breathing zone and mass conservation laws. With the developed model, the ventilation parameters corresponding to different fresh outdoor air ratios are quantified to achieve the targeted indoor air quality (i.e., targeted CO₂ concentration in the breathing zone). Using the fresh outdoor air ratios and corresponding ventilation parameters as inputs, energy performance evaluations of

the air conditioning system are conducted by building energy simulations.

“Machine learning method for real-time non-invasive prediction of individual thermal preference in transient conditions,”

Predicting building occupants' thermal comfort via machine learning (ML) is a hot research topic. Many algorithms and data processing methods have been applied to predict thermal comfort indices in different contexts. But few studies have systematically investigated how different algorithms and data processing methods can influence the prediction accuracy. In this study, we first summarized the recent literature from perspectives of predicted comfort indices, algorithms applied, input features, data sources, sample size, training proportion, predicting accuracy, etc. Then, we applied nine ML algorithms and three data sampling methods to predict the 3-point and 7-point thermal sensation vote (TSV) in ASHRAE Comfort Database II. The results show that with an accuracy of 66.3% and 61.1% for 3-point and 7-point TSV respectively, Random Forest (RF) has the best performance among the tested algorithms. Compared to the Predicted Mean Vote (PMV) model, ML TSV models generally have higher accuracy in TSV prediction. Based on feature importance analysis, the air

temperature, humidity, clothing, air velocity, age, and metabolic rate are the top six important features for TSV prediction.

“Mixed phase Fe₂O₃/Mn₃O₄ magnetic nanocomposite for enhanced adsorption of methyl orange dye: Neural network modeling and response surface methodology optimization,”

In this research, a novel magnetic mesoporous adsorbent with mixed phase of Fe₂O₃/Mn₃O₄ nanocomposite was prepared by a facile precipitating method and characterized extensively. The prepared nanocomposite was used as adsorbent for toxic methyl orange (MO) dye removal from aqua matrix considering its high surface area (178.27 m²/g) with high saturation magnetization (23.07 emu/g). Maximum dye adsorption occurs at solution pH 2.0 and the electrostatic attraction between anionic form of MO dye molecules and the positively charged nanocomposite surface is the main driving force behind this adsorption. Response surface methodology (RSM) was used for optimizing the process variables and maximum MO removal of 97.67% is obtained at optimum experimental condition with contact time, adsorbent

dose and initial MO dye concentration of 45 min, 0.87 g/l and 116 mg/l, respectively. Artificial neural network (ANN) model with optimum topology of 3–5–1 was developed for predicting the MO removal (%), which has shown higher predictive ability than RSM model. Maximum adsorption capacity of this nanocomposite was found to be 322.58 mg/g from Langmuir isotherm model. Kinetic studies reveal the applicability of second-order kinetic model with contribution of intra-particle diffusion in this process.

EXISTING SYSTEM

Agarwal and Sahu [20] conducted air quality prediction studies by employing statistical models. Lary et al. [21] combined remote sensing and meteorological data with groundbased $PM_{2.5}$ observations. Zheng et al. [22] proposed a hybrid prediction method that combines a linear regression-based temporal prediction method with an ANN-based spatial prediction method for pollutant concentrations. Zheng et al. [23] used a data-based approach for the next 48 hours of $PM_{2.5}$ prediction, implementing a prediction model based on linear regression and neural network. They combined meteorological data, weather forecast data, and air quality data from monitoring

stations. Rajput and Sharma [24] used a multiple regression model to represent the changes in air quality index (AQI), considering ambient temperature, relative humidity, and barometric pressure as the main parameters in the regression model for AQI calculation [25].

These classical methods and models all have the advantages of simple algorithms, easy processing, and acceptable prediction results. However, obtaining precise and specific air quality prediction values remains challenging [26].

Disadvantages

- The complexity of data: Most of the existing machine learning models must be able to accurately interpret large and complex datasets to detect Air Quality Index Forecasting.
- Data availability: Most machine learning models require large amounts of data to create accurate predictions. If data is unavailable in sufficient quantities, then model accuracy may suffer.
- Incorrect labeling: The existing machine learning models are only as accurate as the data trained using the input dataset. If the data has been incorrectly labeled, the model cannot make accurate predictions.

Proposed System

In this study, an improved extreme learning machine model based on a genetic algorithm is designed and applied to AQI prediction. To verify the effectiveness of the model, we conducted tests on three real-world datasets. The results confirmed that the proposed method has superior **performance** and outperforms some advanced methods currently

in use. The main contributions of this paper are:

- (1) Modifying the ELM activation function or using the kernel function to improve the prediction accuracy,
- (2) Optimizing the ELM using GA to improve the stability of the results and further enhance the prediction accuracy, and
- (3) Obtaining the correlation analysis results of atmospheric environmental quality prediction parameters by comprehensively considering each relevant factor in line with the actual situation.

Advantages

- The system proposes to optimize the number of ELM hidden layer nodes, thresholds, and weights, along with an improved genetic algorithm (GA) that uses root mean square error (RMSE) as the fitness

function, to obtain the optimal network structure for air quality prediction.

- Air quality forecasting has been a key issue in early warning and control of urban air pollution. The proposed system goal is to anticipate changes in the AQI value at observation points over time.

CONCLUSION

The economic development achieved by the country through rapid urbanization is polluting the environment in an alarming way and putting people's lives in danger. Therefore, a correct analysis and accurate prediction of air quality remains a primary condition to achieve the objective of sustainable development. This paper focuses on the problem of prediction model design, and investigates the problems related to the optimization of the model parameters. A GA-KELM model is designed, implemented, and tested. It is experimentally proven to be more efficient than the classical shallow learning and can effectively explore and learn the interdependence of multivariate air quality correlation time series such as temperature, humidity, wind speed, SO_2 , and PM_{10} .

Therefore, the GA-KELM model developed in this study can be used to provide valuable support to vulnerable groups and trigger early warning of adverse air quality events.

However, there are still areas for further investigation and improvement. In recent years,

numerous advanced algorithms and optimization methods based on genetic algorithms and population intelligence have emerged. Therefore, future research should explore the underlying significance and value of combinatorial intelligence optimization algorithms such as the Limit Learning Machine. Additionally, we acknowledge the need to address the issue of manually setting the number of hidden layer nodes in the optimal Limit Learning Machine. Although the Dynamic Extreme Learning Machine (DELM) algorithm offers adaptive determination of hidden layer nodes without human intervention, further work should be dedicated to this aspect. Moreover, to enhance the accuracy and validity of air quality measurement and assessment, it is crucial to integrate pollutant emission factors and meteorological factors into the evaluation system. This integration will enable a more precise and comprehensive evaluation of air quality.

In conclusion, our study highlights the significance of the GA-KELM model in predicting air quality. We have addressed the optimization challenges and demonstrated its superiority over traditional methods. However, there is still room for improvement and further research. Future studies should delve into advanced optimization algorithms based on genetic algorithms and population intelligence, explore the potential of the Limit Learning Machine, and strive for adaptive determination of hidden layer nodes. Furthermore, the integration of pollutant emission factors and meteorological factors into the evaluation

system will advance the accuracy and reliability of air quality measurement and assessment.

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